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Systematic analysis of the paper “Digital Business Transformation:

An Experience-Based Holistic Framework”

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Abstract

This work is part of the first evaluation of the Advanced IoT course taught by Prof. Dr. Joel Rodrigues, which covers the study, summary, and analysis at a critical development level of publications in renowned institutes to develop an understanding, methodologies, and critical evaluation capacity .

Considering the determined selection process, we selected the topic that covers issues relevant to the initial academic proposal of this doctoral student, regardless of whether it differs from the subject in question. This opportunity proposed by the professor was intended to take advantage of critical development, as well as to add knowledge and material that could enrich or incorporate the final doctoral thesis itself. This helps this student in their academic journey without leaving the main purpose of creating a critical analysis of materials and works proposed by other Doctors on the topics in existing research institutes on the market. Thus, the methodology of this analysis will consist of an introduction, and in a systematic way, we will follow the items of the article under analysis. We will summarize it with notes on each item that requires a critical analysis under the auspices of the author, thus creating a framework of understanding/dissonance to compose a final chapter of suggestions and conclusions. Finally, with this analysis, we will seek to develop a structured critical sense that is easy to understand. Additionally, this work will serve as input for creating the presentation to be given at a future class defense.

Keywords: ANALYSIS, SUMMARY, CRITICAL DEVELOPMENT

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1 Introduction

This work is based on the analysis of the paper: “Digital Business Transformation: An Experience-Based Holistic Framework” [1], which was done by academics Nina Evans [2], Andrej Miklosk [3], Rachele Bosua [4], and Athar Mahmmod Ahmed Qureshi [5].

This work was published by IEEE Access with a focus on surveying market experts selected by the authors to answer the following question: What lessons were learned from digital transformation implementations?

To carry out this research, the researchers adopted the following presentation sequence: introduction; background; research methodology; learnings; discussions; limitations; and suggestions for future research.

Therefore, we will continue with the summaries and analyses of each item that comprise this paper under analysis in the same sequence

2 Analysis by Item

2.1 Introduction

In the form of a literary review that can be seen in the paper's references, researchers speak about organizations, changes and customers, which relate to expectations and desired improvements, using this reviews in all part this paper to development your paper.

Based on their references, which indicate that there are currently many concepts of digital transformation, many of these concepts are contradictory, and therefore, to differentiate this research, they do not use the term digital transformation but rather digital business transformation (DBT).¹

DBT, which in the literature includes improvements in business models and customer experience while taking advantage of digital technologies, is reported to be complex and difficult to implement.

Therefore, analyzing errors and lessons learned is extremely important to consolidate the necessary material for carrying out new steps.²

Therefore, this paper may be useful for executives and managers who wish to transition their businesses to digital.

Ultimately, they determined that the research question was: What are the most important lessons experts have learned about DBT through their extensive experience?

2.2 Background

In this item, the authors divide them into the following three topics:

¹ In this sense, this research seeks to focus on one aspect of the concept of digital transformation, as it is limited to digital business transformation

² It is observed that acting on transformation is mandatory when working with the PDCA methodology, as it involves steps, errors, and successes, indicating that transformation is not an end but rather a process of constant improvement

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A. Digital business transformation

Through constant changes, companies are adjusting their dynamics regarding traditional models in the face of innovations, providing organizations with a continual vision of potential opportunities created by digital technologies across all areas. DBT is a continuous process of improvement in several aspects, including cultural changes necessary for organizations to adapt to the digital era. In this way, DBT not only involves the use of technologies but also requires a shift in management approaches, leadership styles, and governance control methodologies.

B. Misconceptions about DBT

This topic discusses the main misconceptions prevalent in the media regarding DBT, such as: DBT being solely about technology, being akin to any other project within an organization, and being merely another strategic approach for analysis by the company. It suggests that everyone supports the transformation, and entities see it as another project that may be abandoned along the way.

Another existing misconception is that it must be led by the CTO, without much connection to the business area, and that it is confused with digitalization, being an easy-to-implement computerization process.

The barrier to implementing new technologies generates interruptions and hinders the development of the business. The term 'on-going' is very common, leading to a desire for a 'lighter' transformation³.

C. A Holistic View of DBT

DBT should be a program, but there are many wrong approaches, some of which focus more on digitizing processes rather than pursuing trends to achieve growth.

There is an approach that considers DBT as a broad-spectrum concept, focusing on digital resources to obtain results through digitalization. Organizations, therefore, adopt experimental models, with IT as the executor.

Implementing technology is relatively easy, but the organization's culture is crucial to its success. DBT culturally encompasses the entire organization; therefore, failing to understand that it represents a change in paradigms at all levels means that the CEO or Board must be the sponsor who believes in and is focused on the success of DBT, otherwise its viability will be very fragile ⁴

2.3 Research Approach

A. Method

³ In this sense, it is clear that mistakes are actually cultural and vanity barriers, as changes create discomfort for many due to fear and lack the "projects" highlighted in organizations are aimed at growth and status and, often assumed by those in areas that have political power but lacking the competence to conduct them, making their implementation difficult or ineffective.

⁴ This holistic view reflects the complete vision of the digital transformation concept, not just DBT, as DBT is part of the organization's digital transformation.

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An interpretative qualitative approach was used, and after preparation, interviews were conducted so that, after analysis, the presented results could be determined.

The selection of participants was based on purposeful sampling, a non-probabilistic method, based on years of Experience in business and IT, along with their active involvement in leading DBT projects⁵.

Lessons learned from experts were considered more meaningful due to their experience in comparing independent case studies⁶.

B. Participants

Five experts (E1 to E5) were selected according to the validation table and by the researchers.⁷

C. Data Collection and Analysis

The methodology of personal interviews was adopted, focusing on the following question: What lessons did you learn from your experience with Digital Business Transformation implementations?

The interviews were conducted via video conference, focusing on the interviewees' understanding of DBT, their experiences, perceptions, and learnings.

The objective of the interviews was to spare researchers from prior judgment to avoid obtaining generic results⁸.

D. Ethical Considerations

The ethical standards were those approved by the supervising university, seeking to maintain and guarantee all assurances for everyone involved, with participants participating voluntarily, confidentially, and with complete freedom to withdraw from the research at any time. Additionally, total confidentiality for organizations and participants was guaranteed⁹.

2.4 Findings

After conducting the interviews, it became clear that the participants understood that DBT has several interpretations, many of which are incorrect. Therefore, a better analysis is to consider a holistic approach to the topic. The results of these interviews were grouped into six lessons, which will be presented holistically in the

⁵ There is a dissonance when it comes to DBT among the authors, as they consider it a program (continuous act), but sought project specialists (finite act).

⁶ Regardless of the method or participants, it is observed that they adopted experiences as a guide for research and not projects, which makes their experience somewhat restricted

⁷ By adding the score of 6, it becomes clear how this research should be interpreted, as 5 specialists restrict any assessment, given that the low number cannot represent the vast number of specialists using the same criteria around the world in DBT.

⁸ Even with this observation noted, we must consider that the number of people surveyed, and their locations can influence the results of the responses and especially the analysis, as cultural and regional factors are natural influencers. .

⁹ We must pay great attention at this point because ethical issues are based on local cultural factors, as well as the confidentiality of organizations and participants. Without determining at least the region or country, this research must therefore be considered restricted.

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Discussion section.

A. Lesson 1: There Are Many DBT Drivers

The experts' general view points out that the organization's perception must be clear; if it is not, the organization will be doomed to failure and could be excluded from the market, resulting in losses of billions of dollars. The application of DBT must be convincing; otherwise, the organization will tend to return to old practices, abandoning its entire purpose.

The need for DBT must be clear and perceived as completely necessary throughout the organization so that the risks and challenges are much lower compared to the advantages and benefits of implementing DBT.

Innovation is not a driver for DBT if it is not in its DNA; thus, the culture must be continuously developed¹⁰.

B. Lesson 2: Transformation depends on dedicated executives and change leadership

The second lesson addresses the organization's leadership, which must be comprehensive and led by the CEO. The CEO must have a full understanding of DBT and be the primary motivator to ensure that the executives and the Board share the same understanding; otherwise, the probability of failure will be high.

Leadership must be prepared to manage change, especially the CEO, as it is key for challenges and continuous modifications to be implemented so that their subordinates and the Board perceive these changes as positive and clear in the medium and long term.

It is concluded that there must be clear leadership for change, not merely change management. To this end, this change leadership must be inspiring, motivating, and developed for everyone involved. .

C. Lesson 3: DBT must be driven by a focus team established specially for transformation

A specific team must be created to carry out the transformation, and in some cases, it is even necessary to lead this team in a hidden way to implement the transformation.

The transformation team must be focused on tomorrow, distinct from the current operational team. Some interviewees expressed a divergence in understanding, stating that change agents are needed to implement and facilitate the concepts and values of DBT within the current team and among those involved in problem-solving¹¹.

D. Lesson 4: DBT is not primarily about technology but more about people and organizational culture

It is not about technology nor derived from the IT department.

Typically, most projects involve digitalization rather than DBT.

Regardless of the benefits that digitalization can bring, it is not transformation on its own

Transformation is a change in the organization's paradigm that disrupts the entire workforce and causes natural

¹⁰ Analyzing the drivers, the main driver is a total understanding, involvement, and interest from everyone in the organization

¹¹ There is also confusion about DBT and Transformation, perhaps due to this divergence in addition to cultural and regional factors that are not clear in this research.

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resistance to change among human beings.

To implement transformation, the organization must work to understand the culture and values of each area, team, and professional, so that it can transform this resistance into motivating action to drive desire for transformation.

HR will play an important role in training, re-educating, and guiding teams and leaders, not only demonstrating but also convincing them of the improvements and benefits of adopting the transformation.

Even the CIO can be the biggest resistance, as he is the main actor in maintaining the organization's willingness for this cultural change, and to do this, he must have a disruptive mentality.

Thus, transformation is a cultural change, for some a cultural revolution, focusing on the behavior that everyone should adopt, especially management teams¹².

E. Lesson 5: The digital Plataforma "IS" the business

As it is a digital business, the business must be on a digital platform at the center of business activities, as the platform is the business and therefore, it must be adopted and not adapted. That is, when the organization adopts a digital solution for its business, it must adapt to the solution and not adapt the solution to the organization's particularities.

It is observed that the platform must be adopted for the business, not for the process; that is, the digital platform supplier must have the business rules, not the process ¹³.

F. Lesson 6: DBT requires the creation of an ecosystem

The digital platform must be owned and operated by a partner, and all executives, including the Board, must understand that this partner becomes part of the entire DBT ecosystem.

Therefore, the contracting and mode of operation with the partner must be presented with the vision of DBT, as adopting traditional contractual practices may generate conflicts or loss of meaning in the development and maintenance of DBT.

3 Discussion

Therefore, DBT must consider those involved: customers, people, culture, and talents to be successful.

The mandatory prerequisites to start a transformation are as follows:

- i. Absolute support and responsibility of the CEO;
- ii. Senior team dedicated to transformation;

¹² Once again, there is confusion about DBT and Transformation, as this lesson deals with the entire organization and not just with Digital Business Transformation.

¹³ In this item it is observed that the case was seen as DBT, that is, a digital business vision and thus transforming the "digital platform" for the business, not absorbing the processes and thus not being a Digital Transformation but DBT.

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- iii. DBT is about people not technology;
- iv. A strong platform to motivate the organization even in difficulties;
- v. Money to prove the process;
- vi. Time to dedicate yourself to transformation.

The main contribution of this research is the framework demonstrated below:

Figure 1: The DBT Framework

The components of the framework are explain bellow:

A. The framework: Stage 1

Misconceptions about DBT presented in chapter 2.2 item B and Lesson 1

B. The Framework: Stage 2

Readiness for transformation - Lesson 2, 3 and 4

C. The Framework: Stage 3

DBT Challenges - Lesson 3, 4, 5 and 6

D. The Framework: Stage 4¹⁴

3.1 Lessons learned

WHY - Lesson 1

HOW - Lesson 1, 2, 4 e 5

WHO - Lesson 2, 3, 4 e 6

¹⁴ No explanation was put at this stage by the authors, with this they do not define what a Transformed Organization is.

4 Limitations and Suggestions for Future Research

Although our data set is small, each participant has many years of experience, spanning up to 35 years, and respondents only provided their perspectives on DBT in the organizations in which they are involved. Such a study can take either a qualitative or quantitative approach.

Other opportunities for future research include:

- i) focus on one or more industry sectors,
- ii) comparing the sectors, and
- iii) including employee perceptions in the survey.

5 Comments and Conclusion by the Author

The analysis of an article indicates that research is restricted by the small volume of interviewees, which consequently delimits the regions we are aware of, providing us with a limited view.

Even so, we observed that the lessons learned or existing discrepancies—commented on in the notes throughout the work—provide guidance for understanding the concept of Transformation. It should be emphasized that Digital Transformation encompasses the entire organization, and DBT, as proposed in this research, is a part of it, culminating in the adoption of a digital platform to transform the business.

This approach may raise doubts since DBT can be implemented while maintaining all other areas in the traditional way.

In fact, it can be assumed that DBT is a BU (Business Unit) with high independence within the company. Analyzing with broad tolerance, we can consider it a start-up, a 'spin-off' of the digitalized business, categorized when adopting the need for a digital platform, which is mandatory alongside the business rules.

Thus, even though it is a good guide on visions and a restricted analysis of DBT, we conclude that this research and the concepts adopted therein should be reviewed, as confusion sometimes arises on how to apply the framework presented for an organization to carry out its digital transformation or create a digital business unit.

6 References

- [1] N. Evans, A. Miklosik, R. Bosua and A. Mahmood Ahmed Qureshi, "Digital Business Transformation: An Experience-Based Holistic Framework," in IEEE Access, vol. 10, pp. 121930-121939, 2022, [doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3221984](https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3221984).
- [2] NINA EVANS received the bachelor's degree in computer science, the master's degree in information technology, and the M.B.A. and Ph.D. degrees. She is currently an Associate Professor with the UniSA: STEM, University of South Australia. She has worked in various higher education institutions as a Lecturer, an Industry Liaison Manager, an Associate Head of School, the Head of the Department, and the Vice Dean. Her research interests include information and knowledge management, managing the business-IT interface, social networks, and ICT innovation.
- [3] ANDREJ MIKLOSIK is a Professor at the Department of Marketing, Faculty of Management, Comenius University in Bratislava. He has brought his extensive experience from IT project management and consulting into academia. He was the holder of industry certifications including ITIL, PRINCE2, CISA, CISM, CRISC, and CGEIT. He has authored more than 180 publications including numerous monographs and University textbooks focused on IS in business and marketing, digital marketing, IT project management, and knowledge management. Serving the community, he is a reviewer for several IT, marketing, and management journals.
- [4] RACHELLE BOSUA is an Assistant Professor at the Department of Information Science, Open University of the Netherlands. Her research concentrates on the design and adoption of IT artefacts in many different environments and settings (e.g. SMEs and large organizations) to facilitate knowledge sharing, networking, collaboration, and team work. This includes for example virtual communities, coworking hubs, and knowledge-intensive work environments. Her current research interests include knowledge leakage and regulatory frameworks to protect the privacy of individuals in a more connected and digitized world.
- [5] ATHAR QURESHI is currently a senior academic of health services management at the School of Public Health, University of Adelaide. He holds a PhD, a Master in ICT Management and an Honours in Computer Sciences. He is also a certified knowledge manager. Athar's research concentrates on transforming the healthcare workforce, services and organizations. His interests include enterprise transformation, digital transformation, strategic knowledge management, change management, organizational development and behavior management. As a chief investigator, Athar is leading an interdisciplinary team and industry partners studying the strategic consequences of digital transformation of the service industry.